

A zinc phosphate layered biodegradable Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy: Characterization and mechanism of hopeite formation

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Conversion coatings
Hopeite
Zinc
Surface properties
In vitro tests

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to comprehensively investigate the formation mechanism of hopeite on a promising biodegradable Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy during its self-corrosion process and its subsequent influence on the interaction of the material with cells and bacteria. Notably, the self-corrosion process of Zn-based alloys inherently generates Zn²⁺ ions, eliminating the necessity for additional zinc compounds in the treatment. The investigation focused on the chemical composition of the applied baths, exposure time, and temperature, in order to analyze the structure, quality, distribution, phase composition, thickness, and roughness of the resulting layers bringing range of key pros and cons for suggested materials. While the thin layers are considered more beneficial in a wide range of applications, the resulting thinnest layer was observed after exposure to the bath containing additives at 50 °C for 24 h, measuring approximately 192 ± 21 pm in thickness. In addition, the layer possessed the most homogeneous distribution under these conditions. Generally, the layers formed in the bath without additives exhibited higher thickness and rougher surfaces compared to those in the bath containing additives. Such results had a direct impact on dissolution rate, cytotoxicity, and antibacterial properties. The highest dissolution rate (40.7 mg·cm⁻²·day⁻¹) indicating a limited lifetime of the layer was obtained for material processed under the following coating condition: 50 °C, 24 h, and bath without additives. The general presence of surface layers manifested in increased cell viability under direct cytotoxicity test, while smoother surface conditions also supported the antibacterial properties, both making suggested treatments as interesting variations for biodegradable zinc-based materials.

1. Introduction

Biodegradable metals have gained attention since the biomaterials research started to focus on improving implants to promote faster bone healing. As biodegradable materials gradually degrade in the human body, they often consist of essential metallic elements that are absorbed. Hence, the potential implant should be free from toxic metals that cause inflammatory or allergic reactions, leading to the destruction of host tissues and loosening of the implant [1,2]. Therefore, most of

biodegradable alloys are made from magnesium, zinc, and iron [3–5].

Biodegradable implants interact with surrounding tissues and corrosion products form on their surface. These corrosion products could harmfully affect wound healing [6]. The early stages of post-operation are particularly crucial for promoting cell proliferation and growth [7]. The problems concerning degradation rate, as well as biocompatibility, could be solved by alloy coating. The coating is one of the most used surface treatments for metallic surfaces affecting the release of metallic ions into the human body [8,9]. Various surface modification

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2024.130986>

Received 8 April 2024; Received in revised form 4 June 2024; Accepted 5 June 2024

Available online 6 June 2024

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techniques are applied, including deposition of a thin uniform coating, development of a stable passivation oxide layer, ion beam processing for surface modification, or surface texturing [1]. Biocompatible coatings seem to be the most promising for use on biodegradable implants. Besides the barrier effect, such layers are bioactive, resulting in the improvement of the host-implant interactions, osseointegration, and hemocompatibility [1,7].

Coatings applied on biodegradable materials can be consequently divided into two main categories: conversion and deposition coatings [8]. Conversion coatings lead to the full reaction between the metallic substrate and the solution, resulting in the formation of a layer on the modified surface alloy. The resulting protective properties subsequently depend on the type of base metal, thickness, and integrity of the coating [10]. The zinc phosphate coating is the most common one, mainly on magnesium, iron, and titanium alloys [7,11–22]. The coating bath is mainly composed of phosphoric acid and various types of chemical accelerators [23,24]. Those additives are used to affect the process of the coating formation and subsequent properties. The mechanism of the effect of the additive agents on the process of the coating formation is a very complex issue; but its understanding would allow us to adjust the coating properties by modifications of the bath. This article offers a discussion on the influence of individual components present in the bath. The phosphating solutions can be divided into two types [10,25]. The first type is based on the primary alkali metal phosphates and is called actual conversion coatings because the basis metal directly participates in the process [25]. The second type is denoted as pseudo-conversion coating and consists of the contribution of the metal cations present in the solution itself [25]. The formed zinc phosphate coating subsequently could gradually release Zn^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} ions leading to the possible mineralization of bone matrix and facilitation of bone growth [7,26]. It is believed that zinc phosphate coating could have an antibacterial ability and spontaneously form hopeite ($Zn_3(PO_4)_2 \cdot 4 H_2O$, HP) layer significantly enhancing the biocompatibility of the base alloys [3,7]. Moreover, HP coatings possess stable chemistry and good biocompatibility, which is important for biomedical applications [9]. HP is also considered to be versatile biomedical material because it is an important phase in hardened zinc phosphate bone cement [27]. The drawback of such prepared coatings is the non-uniform coverage containing defects such as voids, cracks, holes, or spalling [10]. In contrast to conversion coatings, deposition coatings are created through processes other than chemical reactions. The group of deposition coatings consists of several subgroups that can be categorized by deposition techniques (PVD, CVD) or by the chemical nature of the prepared coating, such as organic (collagen, albumin, PLA = Polylactic acid, PDA = Polydopamine) and inorganic coatings (SiO_2 , TiO_2 , HA = hydroxyapatite). The aim of coatings' preparation is the same as that of conversion coatings and is connected to the enhancement of surface properties and tissue/implant interaction [28].

Alloys based on zinc have gained attention recently in the area of biodegradable metal alloys. Among their advantages mainly include intermediate corrosion rate, fair biocompatibility, no H_2 gas evolution and non-toxic corrosion products, and good processability [2,26,29]. For this reason, zinc alloys are also considered to be the next generation of biodegradable metals for bone-tissue engineering [2–5,29]. On the other hand, *in vivo* studies showed that a locally high concentration of zinc ions inhibits new bone formation [29–31]. For this reason, it is necessary to control the critical concentration of Zn^{2+} ions within the tissue surrounding. Therefore, surface treatment is one of the possibilities how to eliminate the release of zinc ions and improve the biocompatibility [29]. The excess of released Zn^{2+} ions could be incorporated into the surface layer, and appropriate levels of concentration of the Zn^{2+} ions could be beneficial for bone healing [29]. Moreover, surface treatment is a simple, effective, and lower-cost way for solving all previously mentioned issues – mainly release of Zn^{2+} ions [8]. However, surface treatments of zinc alloys are rather scarce in the literature, in contrast with the surface modification of magnesium and

iron-based alloys. Some attempts have been undertaken on the surface modification of zinc for implants [31]. The coatings were based on polymer, micro-arc oxidation, or conversion coatings [29,32–36]. The reduction of the corrosion rate and simultaneous improvement of biocompatibility were successful. Unfortunately, the suitability of these coatings for orthopedic implants was not sufficient in terms of osteogenesis, osteoconduction, and bone resorption [31]. Among the mentioned coatings, HP conversion coating exhibited good corrosion protection ability and cytocompatibility to the bone-related cells [29,31,35]. Conversion coatings belong to the low-cost and easily implemented surface treatment techniques as was mentioned above [10]. However, the HP coatings have still deficiencies in terms of bio functionalities, especially osteogenic and angiogenic properties. HP coatings have a lot of space to improve since their functionality depends largely on the varying characteristics such as the microstructure of coated alloys, morphology, and roughness of the formed layer. These problems have not been solved yet and, therefore, the research in the design of HP coatings on zinc alloys continues. In work [3] was shown that the interfacial HP is the most important for the controlling of biocompatibility of zinc. As the zinc alloys dissolve during conversion coating, various products form on the surface. These products are insoluble and composed mostly of HP, which may be accompanied zinc oxide (ZnO), and zinc hydroxide ($Zn(OH)_2$) [3,23,37]. In the work [35], it was claimed that the HP layer has stable chemical property and provides good biocompatibility which makes it a promising coating material.

Up to this time, only a few of works focusing mainly on surface treatments of pure zinc have been published. Du et al. [8] presented the effect of short-term chemical conversion on the microstructure, corrosion resistance, and wettability of Zn-Mg-Ca alloy. Qian et al. [29] presented a hybrid coating consisting of bioactive molecules and calcium phosphate on the Zn substrate. They showed that the release of Zn^{2+} was slower and could be controlled. Besides, the coating exhibited satisfying osteogenic and angiogenic properties. Zhang et al. [9] presented the enhanced corrosion resistance of HP coating with graphene oxide on pure zinc. The study [4] showed the successful application of magnesium-based coating fabricated on pure zinc in terms of corrosion rate and cytocompatibility. Most of these works were focused only on the conversion coatings of pure zinc and a fraction of studies about coated zinc alloys for biomedical applications has been published.

To the best of our knowledge, no studies focusing on the characterization of surface modification of zinc-based alloys have been published. Publications mostly focus on characterization of layers on zinc substrate using electrochemical methods. As was mentioned in the work [27], the research of coatings on metal implants is in the initial stage and it will take decades to achieve its application in the human body. Our work fills the gap and paves the new way in this field of research. This work can be divided into two parts. The first part focuses on characterizing the resulting layer formed after exposing the alloy in different types of baths at various temperatures and times. The baths differed in the addition of compounds that influenced the growth process and the characteristics of the layer. In this part, the phase composition of the resulting layer, its morphology, the change in weight of the substrate with the layer, the change in weight of just the layer, its thickness, and roughness were analyzed and monitored. Additionally, the pH development in the bath and the dissolution rate of the substrate were monitored to determine the effect of Zn^{2+} ions, which were not pre-added to the bath. The second part focused on cell testing of the alloy with the layer formed under different conditions. The obtained results were discussed in terms of the influence of individual bath components and exposure conditions (temperature, time), pH, Zn^{2+} ion concentration, cytotoxicity, cell adhesion, and antibacterial properties. The aim of this paper is to investigate the mechanism of the layer formation under various reaction condition. We tested two types of phosphating bath to obtain uniform layer without the presence of defects on the biodegradable cast zinc alloy Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr (wt%). This alloy, based on our previous studies,

appears to be the most promising alloy for use as a biomaterial [38–40]. A layer based on hopeite is suitable in terms of chemical composition, as compounds containing phosphate anions contribute to the mineralization of bone tissue. The formed layers were characterized by various experimental techniques followed by the subsequent *in vitro* tests (Murine fibroblasts L929 and Human fetal osteoblasts hFOB 1.19) to the assessment of the biological aspect.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Material preparation

A cast zinc alloy Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr (wt%) was used as the substrate. Pure zinc (99.95 wt%), magnesium (Magnesium Elektron, 99.95 wt%), and strontium (Strem Chemicals, 99.9 wt%) were used for the preparation of this ternary alloy. The alloy was prepared by casting in an electrical resistance furnace without protective atmosphere. Zinc was melted at 550 °C in a graphite crucible and subsequently Mg and Sr were added in the form of pure metals. Melt was homogenized for 10 min in the furnace and then casted into the brass mold at 25 °C. The nominal composition was verified by AAS (atomic absorption spectrometer). Parts of the obtained ingots were dissolved in nitric acid and analyzed using an AGILENT 280 FS. Analysis of chemical composition confirmed the required chemical composition: 99.02:0.81:0.17 (weight ratio) for Zn:Mg:Sr. The sheets with approximate dimensions of 20 mm × 20 mm × 5 mm (the size of the individual samples was measured for the appropriate determination of the exposed surface area of the sample) were ground using a series of SiC sandpapers up to P1200 grit, ultrasonically cleaned by deionized water, ethanol, and dried. Subsequently, the sheets were pickled in 10 wt% of HNO₃ (Lach-ner, s.r.o., 65 %) for 1–2 s for surface activation (images are shown in Supplementary data), rinsed by ethanol, dried, and such prepared samples were weighed, obtaining m_1 . In total 5 samples were hung on hooks using PTFE seal tape and then exposed to two types of baths.

Alloy containing predominantly Mg₂Zn₁₁ phase was prepared using pure Zn and Mg and melted under an Ar atmosphere in induction furnace. Subsequently, the alloy was annealed at 350 °C for 24 h to homogenize the phase composition. The composition of the prepared alloy was determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) as follows: 95 wt% of Mg₂Zn₁₁ and 5 wt% of pure Zn. Such prepared sample was used to demonstrate the potential formation of the MgF₂ phase from the Mg₂Zn₁₁ phase. The sample containing predominantly Mg₂Zn₁₁ phase was exposed to the bath type "1" at 25 °C for 1 h.

2.2. Coating preparation

In this study, the phosphating bath was inspired by the bath used in work L.Y. Niu, et al [17] and subsequently modified to decrease the number of the components and thus prepare the referential layers. The chemical composition of the baths together with the process conditions are listed in Table 1. All the solutions were prepared with analytical

Table 1
Chemical composition of the baths used for the phosphating process.

Type of bath	Bath composition	Concentration (g·L ⁻¹)	Treatment conditions
"1"	Phosphoric acid	17.50	25 °C; 37 °C; 50 °C 1; 2; 4; 6; 24 h
	Sodium fluoride	1.70	
	N-Ethylethanamine	0.43	
	2,3-Dihydroxybutanedioic acid	2.20	
	Sodium nitrate	0.17	
	Sodium nitrite	0.83	
"2"	Phosphoric acid	17.50	
	Sodium nitrate	0.17	
	Sodium nitrite	0.83	

grade chemical compounds: phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄, Lach-Ner, s.r.o., 85 %), sodium fluoride (NaF, Penta s.r.o.), N-Ethylethanamine (diethylamine, Sigma-Aldrich), 2,3-Dihydroxybutanedioic acid (tartaric acid, HO₂CCH(OH)CH(OH)CO₂H, Penta s.r.o.), sodium nitrate (NaNO₃, Penta s.r.o.), and sodium nitrite (NaNO₂, Penta s.r.o.). The NaF and N-Ethylethanamine were used as anticorrosion agents, HO₂CCH(OH)CH(OH)CO₂H was employed to reduce the production of sludge, and NaNO₃ and NaNO₂ were used as accelerators for better formation of coating in the phosphating bath. The specimens were treated in a phosphating solution at 25; 37, and 50 ± 1 °C for 1; 2; 4; 6, and 24 h with constant stirring (250 rpm). The concentration of Zn²⁺ ions released in the baths was analyzed by atomic absorption spectrometer Agilent 280FS AA. The samples were collected into the beakers for the following times: 1; 2; 4; 6, and 24 h. Aliquots of 10 mL were withdrawn for the analysis. The final filtrate after cooling was analyzed as well. The pH of the phosphating baths was measured after the mixing of solution, at reaching the exposure temperature, after 1; 2; 4; 6, and 24 h at exposure temperature, and after cooling to the laboratory temperature. The pH value was measured using an XS Instruments pH meter with a Hamilton electrode. The phosphating solution was filtrated after 24 h of exposure to find out the possible sedimentation of particles formed by changes in the equilibrium in the solution. However, the presence of sediments was not observed during this procedure.

After the coating process, all the coated sheets were rinsed with ethanol and dried for further weighing. The weight changes after the coating process were determined by the accurate weighting of the samples before and after processing and according to Eq. (1).

$$\Delta m_{\text{substrate+coating}} = m_1 - m_2 \quad (1)$$

where m_1 is the zinc alloy weight before phosphating, m_2 is the weight of the coated zinc alloy.

The specific weight of the prepared phosphate layer ($m_{\text{pickling weight}}$) per unit area was calculated according to Eq. (2):

$$\Delta m_{\text{pickling weight}} = \frac{m_2 - m_3}{A} \quad (2)$$

where m_3 is the weight of zinc alloy after the chemical removing of the phosphate layer, and A is the surface area of the sample before the exposure to bath. The surface layers were dissolved in chromic acid (0.5 g·L⁻¹ CrO₃ according to ASTM E407 standard) at 75 ± 1 °C followed by weighing to obtain constant weight. The thickness of the obtained layers was determined using pickling results and was estimated by Eq. (3). Triplicate samples were used to determine the coating weight and the average values with standard deviations were reported.

$$h = \frac{m}{\rho \cdot S} \quad (3)$$

where h is thickness of hopeite coating, m is weight of hopeite, ρ is density of hopeite, S is surface of sample.

2.3. Surface characterization

The elemental composition and morphology of the formed layers were analyzed by scanning electron microscope Tescan Vega 3 LMU equipped with energy dispersive spectrometer OXFORD Instruments X-max EDS SDD 20 mm² (SEM-EDS). The sheet was placed on a graphite double-sided adhesive conductive tape. To overcome the problem of surface charging during SEM-EDS analysis and to improve surface conductivity, the surface of the sample was sputtered with a layer of gold using Rotary-Pumped Sputter Coater (QUORUM Q150R ES) to the thickness of 5 nm prior to the SEM analysis. The phase composition was determined by XRD. PANalytical X'Pert PRO diffractometer with Co-anode ($\lambda_{K\alpha 1} = 0.1789$ nm, $\lambda_{K\alpha 2} = 0.1793$ nm) in Bragg-Brentano (BB) geometry was used. To demonstrate the possibility of MgF₂ formation on Mg₂Zn₁₁ phase, as-cast Mg₂Zn₁₁ phase was exposed to the bath type "1"

at 25 °C for 1 h and analyzed using the two following XRD setup: i) Bragg-Brentano geometry employing PANalytical X'Pert PRO with Cu anode and effective penetration depth $D_{99\%}$ in Mg_2Zn_{11} of approx. ~ 30 μm for $2\theta = 60^\circ$ (penetration depth changes with angle, Cu anode was chosen to enable a direct comparison with the following setup); ii) grazing incidence diffraction (GID): Rigaku SmartLab with Cu anode in parallel beam geometry, incident angle 0.5° . Effective penetration depth $D_{99\%}$ in Mg_2Zn_{11} is approx. 550 nm (penetration depth is constant). Phase composition was established by Rietveld refinement using the TOPAS suite.

The confocal laser scanning microscope LEXT OLS 3100 (Olympus Corp.) was used to evaluate the surface morphology and roughness according to the ISO 25178 standard. Images were captured in confocal mode using the 408 nm wavelength laser diode with 10 x or 50 x objective lens (resulting in 240 x or 1200 x total magnification, resp.) with about 200 scan steps in the z axis. All images were preprocessed with spike removal and, if necessary, surface tilt correction. The average surface roughness was calculated using the LEXT OLS software from the whole surface area of three images with a total magnification of 1200 \times .

2.4. Material exposure in medium

Cylindrical samples (height 3 mm, diameter 10 mm) with different surface treatment and untreated ones (for comparison) were sterilized by 70 % ethanol (1 h) and by UV light (2 h). Samples were placed in 12-well plate and 2 mL of DMEM/Ham's F-12 (Sigma, D6434) medium with 10 % FBS (Sigma F7524), 2.5 mM L-glutamine (Sigma, G8541) was added (Surface/Volume was 1.25 cm^2/mL). Surface/Volume was 1.25 cm^2/mL according to the ISO standard no10933: Biological evaluation of medical devices. The samples were placed to standard cultivation conditions of 37 °C, 5 % CO_2 and 100 % relative humidity. After 24 h, samples were dried, sputter coated with gold (10 nm thick layer, Leica EM ACE600) and observed with SEM.

2.5. Cell cultivation

Murine fibroblasts L929 (ATCC® CCL-1™) were maintained in MEM (Sigma, M0446) medium with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS, Sigma F7524) at standard conditions of 37 °C, 5 % CO_2 and 100 % relative humidity. Cells were passaged regularly using trypsin-EDTA solution (Sigma, T4049). Human fetal osteoblasts hFOB 1.19 (ATCC® CRL-11372™) were maintained in DMEM/Ham's F-12 (Sigma, D6434) medium with 10 % FBS (Sigma F7524), 2.5 mM L-glutamine (Sigma, G8541) and selection reagent G418 (Sigma, G8168) at permissive temperature of 34 °C, with 5 % CO_2 and 100 % relative humidity. Cells were passaged regularly using trypsin-EDTA solution without phenol red (Gibco, 15400054). Both cell lines were used from 3rd passage after thawing and only till 20th passage.

2.6. Test on extracts

On day one, L929 or hFOB 1.19 were trypsinized and resuspended in cultivation medium to obtain a suspension with a concentration of $1 \cdot 10^5$ or $2 \cdot 10^5$ cells per mL, respectively. Thereafter, 100 μL of the cell suspension was seeded into a 96-well plate, which means the seeding density of $1 \cdot 10^4$ and $2 \cdot 10^4$ cells per well for L929 and hFOB 1.19, respectively.

Cylindrical samples (height 3 mm, diameter 10 mm) with different surface treatment (samples exposed at 25 °C for 1 h in the bath type "1" were tested only with L929, Table 4) and untreated ones (for comparison) were sterilized by 70 % ethanol (1 h) and by UV light (2 h). This sterilization procedure is commonly used for degradable metallic materials [41]. Thereafter, samples were transferred to 3 mL of appropriate cultivation medium supplemented with reduced concentration of FBS (5 %, as suggested by ISO 10993-5 standard [42]) without G418 and agitated (130 RPM) at 37 °C in closed vessels for 24 h. The surface to

volume ratio was $0.875 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ for all samples, which is 1.4 x higher than the ratio recommended in the ISO standard. Higher extraction volume is more suitable for degradable metallic biomaterials [43]. Three triplicates were used for each sample.

On day two, the medium in 96-well plates was replaced by the extracts prepared as described above. The extracts were used undiluted, (100 % extracts) and two-fold diluted (50 % extracts). Six technical replicates were used for each sample. Sole cultivation medium served as negative control, 0.5 % solution of Tween-20 as a positive (cytotoxic) control. The concentration of released ions in the extracts after addition of ultrapure HNO_3 (10 $\mu\text{L} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) was measured by ICP-MS (Perkin Elmer Elan 6000 spectrometer, three measurements for each sample).

On day three, after 24 ± 1 h incubation at 34 or 37 °C with the extracts, cell metabolic activity was evaluated by resazurin assay. Resazurin is metabolized to resorufin by living cells [44]. Extracts were removed and resazurin solution (final concentration 25 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) in cultivation medium without phenol red was added. After 2 h of incubation in case of L929 and 4 h in case of hFOB 1.19, fluorescence at 560/590 nm (excitation/emission) was measured (Fluoroskan Ascent FL, Thermo, or Spectramax id5, Molecular Devices). Cytotoxicity of the extracts was calculated as a percentage of metabolic activity of the negative control. Extracts causing the decrease below 70 % of the activity of the control were considered cytotoxic, as described in the ISO 10993-5 standard.

2.7. Cell adhesion

The selected samples (14 mm in diameter and 3 mm in height) were placed in 24-well plates. The sample without a surface treatment was also used. Titanium was used as a negative control. hFOB 1.19 were resuspended in cultivation medium with 10 % FBS and without G418 and seeded directly on to the samples. The seeding density was 50,000 cells $\cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$. hFOB 1.19 were used instead of L929 cells due to their closer resemblance to osteoblasts.

After 24 h, the medium was removed, samples were rinsed with PBS (phosphate buffered saline) and cells were fixed with ice-cold methanol for 5 min. Thereafter, F-actin was stained with TRITC-phalloidin and nuclei were stained with DAPI and samples were observed using Olympus BX53. The whole surface of each sample was scanned at a magnification of 100 x and tile images were made for each sample. Area of 40 mm^2 was selected for each sample and number of nuclei per cm^2 was determined using ImageJ software. Detailed images at magnification of 200 x were also obtained for each sample. For selected samples, the concentration of released ions to the removed cultivation media was measured by ICP-MS as described in Section 2.6.

2.8. Antibacterial activity

Antibacterial tests were performed with *Escherichia coli* (DBM 3138) as a representative of Gram-negative bacteria and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (ATCC14998 CCM21245) representing Gram-positive bacteria. The test was performed as in [45] to followed by drip method [46].

A bacterial suspension was prepared the day before the test. Bacteria were inoculated into the liquid Luria-Bertani (LB) medium (Lennox) and incubated at 37 °C overnight. At the day of the experiment, bacterial suspension was diluted with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) to a turbidity of 1 McFarland Standard (which corresponds to approx. $3 \cdot 10^8$ CFU $\cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ for *E. coli*). Thereafter, serial dilution was prepared (Tables 2 and 3). The specimens (height 3 mm, diameter 10 mm) with different surface treatment (Table 4) were sterilized by 70 % ethanol (1 h) and by UV light (2 h) and then submerged into 2 mL of bacterial suspension - dilutions no. 6 and no. 3–4 for *E. coli* and *S. epidermidis*, respectively (Tables 2 and 3) to obtain countable number of colonies and left for 4 h in laboratory temperature. The specimens obtained under given conditions were selected on the base of the results from SEM and confocal microscopy and should represented all types of surfaces after different

Table 2

Serial dilution of *E. coli*. All dilutions were ten-fold apart from the seventh which was two-fold. McF = McFarland. CFU = colony forming units.

	1 McF	0.1 McF	0.01 McF etc.					
Dilution no.	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	
Theoretical number of CFU of <i>E. coli</i> per mL	$3 \cdot 10^8$	$3 \cdot 10^7$	$3 \cdot 10^6$	$3 \cdot 10^5$	$3 \cdot 10^4$	$3 \cdot 10^3$	$1.5 \cdot 10^3$	

Table 3

Serial dilution of *S. epidermidis*. All dilutions were ten-fold apart from the fourth which was two-fold. McF = McFarland.

	1 McF	0.1 McF	0.01 McF	0.001	0.0005 McF
Dilution no.	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.

Table 4

Sample designation for cells tests.

Type of bath	Temperature (°C)	Exposure (h)	Label
"1"	25	1	1_25_1 h
	37	1	1_37_1 h
	37	6	1_37_6 h
	50	1	1_50_1 h
	50	24	1_50_24 h
"2"	25	1	2_25_1 h
	37	1	2_37_1 h
	37	6	2_37_6 h
	50	1	2_50_1 h
	50	24	2_50_24 h

exposures. Three replicates were used for each type of material. The samples without any treatment were used for comparison and copper was used as a positive (antibacterial) control. Negative control (suspension without any samples) was used as a control of bacterial growth. The surface to volume ratio was $1.25 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$. At the same time, 100 μL of the suspensions of dilutions no. 7 and no. 5 for *E. coli* and *S. epidermidis*, respectively (Tables 2 and 3) were spread on a Petri dish containing Plate Count Agar (PCA) as a control of dilution accuracy (in triplicates).

After 4 h, drip test was performed by transferring 25 μL of suspension into each field of Petri dish (PCA) divided in twelve squares. One Petri dish contained four drops (of 25 μL) of each triplicate from one specimen. Every type of specimen was applied on one dish. Furthermore, subsequent dilution, blank (pure PBS) and a control dish (bacterial suspension without samples) were prepared using the same drip method. The plates were then left at the laboratory temperature and the next day transferred to 37 °C until the colonies on control dish were visible and suitable for counting. Colonies on plates were counted using Schuett Count. The colonies counts were compared to the count on the control dish.

3. Results

3.1. Phase composition of coatings

The phase compositions of the HP coatings prepared under various phosphating conditions are listed in Table 5. As can be seen, the XRD phase analysis indicated the presence of Zn, $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$, and SrZn_{13} phases coming from the alloy itself (see Fig. S1 and Table S1 in Supplementary data). In some cases, peaks belonging to hopeite from the formed HP layer were observed. Our previous published work [40,47,48] showed and described the microstructure of the alloy used as the substrate in this

Table 5

Quantitative phase analysis (XRD) of HP coatings formed after an exposure under various conditions.

Type	Time (h)	Phase composition (wt%)			
		Zn	$\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$	SrZn_{13}	HP
Type "1" 25 °C	1	89.2	4.8	6.0	–
	2	86.3	4.7	9.0	–
	4	83.8	3.6	12.6	–
	6	83.3	3.4	13.0	0.4
	24	46.1	3.5	15.7	34.8
	Type "1" 37 °C	1	90.9	3.6	5.5
2		90.8	1.8	7.5	–
4		87.1	1.9	11.0	–
6		84.3	1.3	12.0	2.4
24		31.2	0.7	5.4	62.7
Type "1" 50 °C		1	59.1	10.8	4.1
	2	58.8	8.7	3.6	28.9
	4	52.2	9.1	4.7	34.0
	6	60.5	6.8	3.8	58.9
	24	52.3	8.4	4.3	35.0
	Type "2" 25 °C	1	89.6	5.1	5.3
2		88.0	4.6	7.5	–
4		87.9	2.7	9.4	–
6		79.9	2.9	16.1	1.1
24		36.3	1.9	8.0	53.8
Type "2" 37 °C		1	83.7	5.2	11.1
	2	82.4	5.6	12.0	–
	4	60.6	4.4	11.6	23.4
	6	57.1	5.6	5.5	31.8
	24	50.4	6.7	4.1	38.8
	Type "2" 50 °C	1	82.2	3.8	8.4
2		79.1	2.8	15.4	2.7
4		57.4	6.6	16.5	19.5
6		56.4	4.2	12.4	27.0
24		65.0	5.6	10.6	18.8

study. Based on the results, we can claim that the formed layer was not composed of phases originally occurring in the substrate. The determined content of zinc significantly decreased with prolonged of exposure time at 25 °C in the bath type "1". It is important to note that the XRD signal was obtained from an approximate depth of up to 30 μm from the surface of the sample. The same situation was observed in the case of the $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$ phase, but the decrease was not as sharp as in the case of Zn. Conversely, the content of the SrZn_{13} phase increased with time. HP was detected in a minor amount after 6 h of exposure at 25 °C and further increased after the exposure lasting 24 h. A similar trend was observed after the exposure at 37 °C. More precisely, the representation of Zn, as well as the $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$ phase, decreased again, but the decrease of the amount of $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$ phase was much faster than that of during phosphating at 25 °C. On the other hand, the volume fraction of the SrZn_{13} phase fluctuated with a final decrease in its amount. The presence of HP was found after 6 h by XRD analysis; nevertheless, its volume fraction was almost doubled after 24 h at 37 °C in comparison with the quantity determined after 24 h at 25 °C (Table 5). For the highest treatment temperature of 50 °C, HP was detected already after 1 h of exposure and the highest value of determined content was found to be after 6 h. From the initial stage of exposure at 50 °C, the content of Zn was the lowest across the selected reaction conditions after the exposure for 1 h, but the determined values were nearly for 24 h. The results indicated the reduction of the zinc intensity as the substrate is more covered by layer. It can be inferred that this observation is applicable to all the measured diffraction patterns of substrates exposed for 6 and 24 h, as the coverage by the layer is expected to increase. The constant representation was also observed in the case of the SrZn_{13} phase. On the contrary, the quantity of the $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$ phase was found to be the highest after the exposure at 50 °C. The trend of changes in the phase composition and volume fractions determined after the exposure in the bath type "2" remained similar to the changes observed after phosphating in the bath type "1". The exposure in the bath type "2" at 25 °C did not affect the results of phase composition significantly. The systematic changes in

the quantity of single phases were similar for Zn and the Mg_2Zn_{11} . A slight increase was detected for the $SrZn_{13}$, where the highest representation was found after 6 h of exposure (Table 5). The presence of HP was revealed after 6 h, but its content was more dominant after 24 h than in the case of HP formed during phosphating in the bath type "1". Overall, the amount of Zn, Mg_2Zn_{11} , and $SrZn_{13}$ phases was considerably lower. The temperature increase to 37 °C in the bath type "2" slower decrease of Zn quantity compared to as in the alloy exposed to the same temperature in the bath type "1". The determined content of the Mg_2Zn_{11} phase increased slightly in contrast with the $SrZn_{13}$ phase. HP was detected already after 4 h of exposure and its volume fraction did not exceed that in the bath type "1". The qualitative analysis of the phase composition belonging to HP on zinc substrate exposed to 50 °C in the bath type "2" did not deviate. HP was already found after 1 h again and its total amount was lower in comparison to its volume fraction found after phosphating in the bath type "1". The individual diffraction patterns are shown in the Supplementary data. Nevertheless, minor changes in quantities of these phases can also be ascribed to slight variations in texture across individual samples and differences in surface roughness.

3.2. Morphology characterization of HP coatings formed on the substrate

Based on the results of the XRD analyses, the formed layer was determined to be HP on the zinc substrate. The HP layers morphology on the surface of Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr substrate exposed to the bath type "1" at various phosphating times and temperatures was evaluated by SEM (Fig. 1). There are noticeable differences in the presence of cracks and pores, the shape and size of crystals, and in uniformity and compactness of HP coating suggesting crucial influence of time and temperature on HP crystal nucleation and subsequent layer growth. The mildest condition (25 °C, 1 h) caused the formation of HP nuclei (highlighted by red

circles) mainly along the zinc dendrites. The visible etched areas were filled with HP and small flower-like crystals of HP were also randomly distributed over the zinc dendrites. Such a condition was sufficient for the formation of many small crystals of HP on the zinc alloy even though the surface was not fully covered. As the time was prolonged to 6 h and 24 h at 25 °C, the zinc dendrites were covered more densely, and the regions of small-like crystals were gradually transformed into the large plate-like polyhedral HP crystals observed after 24 h of exposure. Crystals exhibited irregular shapes and non-uniform dimensions. Exposure at 37 °C accelerated the formation of HP. The small-like crystals joined together and formed clusters on the original zinc dendrites after exposure lasting 1 h. The etched regions between zinc dendrites were filled with HP as well, however, there were obvious holes in contrast with HP obtained at 25 °C. The morphology of HP coating after 6 h of exposure was similar to the morphology of coating after 6 h at 25 °C. The zinc dendrites were more etched, and these areas were replaced by formed HP. Simultaneously, small flower-like crystals were connected resulting in the partial coverage of zinc dendrites by HP. The fine pores within the crystals were also observed with the increase of time to 6 h. With the increase of the exposure time to 24 h at 37 °C, the layer of HP became much more uniform with small regions/gaps with uncovered zinc dendrites. However, the resulted layer was not smooth due to the presence of large polyhedral crystals. The selected temperature of 50 °C allowed the formation of a uniform layer whose surface wrinkled with voids. The formation of HP nuclei was faster and HP crystals covered densely the whole substrate. HP crystals were growing in the tendency to embrace together upon increase phosphating temperature. The surface was improved with increased exposure time and a relatively smooth layer with rarely present voids was obtained after 24 h. Cracks were observed on the coating, but no large polyhedral crystals were present. The growth of HP was multidirectional over the surface and hopeite

Fig. 1. SEM micrographs of HP coating formed on the surface of Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy exposed to the bath type "1".

$(\text{Zn}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O})$ crystals tended to grow in random orientation after all tested experimental conditions.

The illustrated SEM-EDS maps are shown in Fig. 2a, b. EDS analyses revealed the occurrence of zinc, magnesium, and strontium (Fig. 2a) visible on SEM micrographs. The presence of hopeite is represented by the map for phosphorus and this map showed the isolated isles of hopeite as well as the partially connected nets of them. The map belonging to oxygen corresponded to the map of phosphorus and therefore, its map is not shown in Fig. 2. These maps could be considered the same for all samples exposed to 25 and 37 °C. The highest applied temperature 50 °C allowed the formation of a uniform layer across the whole substrate as was described above. The layer contained voids through which the zinc alloy substrate could be detected (Fig. 2b). The areas containing increased concentration of strontium were also found and probably correspond to the SrZn_{13} phase.

Fig. 3 shows the morphology of the HP layer prepared on the zinc alloy substrate at various phosphating conditions in the bath type "2". The bath type "2" containing phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4), sodium nitrate (NaNO_3), and sodium nitrite (NaNO_2) caused the faster formation of HP. The quality of these coatings was worse compared to those prepared in the bath type "1" (Fig. 1). The coating obtained after 1 h at 25 °C consisted of small flower-like crystals (highlighted by red circle) with small voids and the zinc substrate was more etched in comparison with the surface obtained under the same condition in the bath type "1". Moreover, the formation of small flower-like crystals was observed only at specific locations (etched regions). The results of the EDS analysis for these conditions are provided in the Supplementary data. The etched regions were gradually filled by HP which had still a small flower-like shape after 6 h of exposure. These crystals were arranged into the larger clusters suggesting the agglomeration of present crystals. The

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of HP coating formed on the surface of Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy exposed to the bath type "2".

polyhedral needle-like crystals were elongated after 24 h of the exposure and the clusters aggregated and were more massive. Nevertheless, the zinc substrate was not covered completely. The morphology of HP coating with a reaction time of 1 h resembled the honeycombs when the

Fig. 2. SEM-EDS maps of HP coating formed on the surface of Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy exposed to the bath type "1" for a) 6 h at 37 °C and b) 24 h at 50 °C.

zinc alloy was exposed to 37 °C. The honeycombs were destroyed after 6 h leading to the formation of round lumps. This did not change after 24 h of the exposure. Round lumps of HP crystals were also generated on the zinc substrate with this reaction time. Their distribution was random, but the majority of crystals was inserted into areas between zinc dendrites. The surface was more etched and wrinkled. It seemed that the further development of a continuous HP layer was prevented. The same situation was observed on the substrate with reaction times of 1 and 6 h at 50 °C. The surface was attacked as in the case of alloys exposed to 37 °C but the typical etched regions were denser covered along the zinc dendrites. The morphology of obtained layer with a reaction time of 24 h revealed the formation of well-crystallized phosphate crystals with uniform surface coverage over the entire surface of zinc alloys. In contrast with the bath type "1", the surface was full of voids and single clusters of HP. These clusters were not already observed after the exposure in the bath type "1". The bath type "1", as well as bath type "2", therefore prevented the formation of large polyhedral crystals of HP at 50 °C. Nevertheless, the layer obtained after the exposure in the bath type "2" seemed to be more discontinuous in comparison with the layer obtained in the bath type "1". There is no evidence that the crystals were oriented in a specific direction.

The presence of P, O (map corresponding to P), Zn, Mg, and Sr as major elements (Fig. 4) suggested that the coating formed on zinc alloy substrate is indeed an alloy covered by zinc phosphate. The spectrum of element Zn might be derived from the coating or the matrix. When the condition temperature was 37 °C and the time reached 6 h, the presence of SrZn₁₃ phase was more evident. In the same areas even accompanied the occurrence of HP (Fig. 4a). EDS analysis on these regions indicated that these white flowers-like crystals consist of HP with 7.5 wt% of Sr and 8.9 wt% of O. However, XRD analysis did not prove the possible

incorporation of Sr into the phosphate or the formation of another phase (Table 5). Therefore, it could be concluded that it is probably SrZn₁₃ phase. According to the EDS elemental analysis of the layer obtained after exposure at 50 °C (Fig. 4b), HP created the whole coating except the presence of voids. The EDS results indicated that the coating mainly contained P, O, and Zn.

The coating mass is one of the prime factors widely used to assess the phosphating process and its progress. Hence, the weight changes are presented in this work. We are aware of the dissolving/self-corrosion of the substrate during the exposure and these results are only for monitoring the change in substrate weight with already formed layer. The average weight change of substrate with formed layer (exposed area of samples was similar for each phosphated sample) was calculated according to Eq. (1) and the results are shown in Fig. 5a, b. This calculation comprises the weight of the sample before and after the exposure (commonly used method) and thus includes the formed layer and dissolving itself. The changes in weight of substrate with layer during exposure in the bath type "1" at various temperatures increased almost linearly with the time (Fig. 5a). The sharpest slope of the curve belonging to the average weight of the layer was observed at 25 °C. Nevertheless, the highest increase was determined for the exposure at 37 °C and the lowest for 50 °C where the most uniform layer formed (Fig. 1). The average value of pH was measured to be 1.81 ± 0.03 after mixing of bath type "1" at ambient and higher exposure temperatures as well. The solution was acidic during the entire reaction time with a gradual increase in pH value. The resulting pH was approximately similar for all conditions in the bath type "1". The weight development in time was similar in the bath type "2" as in the bath type "1". The highest weight change was observed during exposure at 25 °C; although, the changes were lower up to 6 h in comparison with 37 and 50 °C (Fig. 5b).

Fig. 4. SEM-EDS maps of HP coating formed on the surface of Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy exposed to the bath type "2" for a) 6 h at 37 °C and b) 24 h at 50 °C.

Fig. 5. Average weight change of substrate with formed layer obtained at various times and temperatures of phosphating in the bath a) type "1" and b) type "2". Measured pH values are represented by points at dashed lines.

The lowest change in weight of the layer was found after exposure lasting 24 h at 50 °C which was similar to the exposure in the bath type "1". Overall, the weight changes measured after phosphating at all temperatures in the bath type "2" were higher than that in the bath type "1". Therefore, the coating obtained in the bath type "1" was lighter than that in the bath type "2". The initial pH after mixing of the solution was determined to be 1.50 ± 0.05 suggesting the bath type "2" was more acidic. The value of pH increased in all cases but the most distinctive one was observed during exposure at 50 °C. However, the resulting values of pH were similar for all conditions.

Coating thickness is usually quantified in terms of weight per unit area ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and is referred to as coating weight [49]. It is crucial to note that all calculation assumes a 100 % layer density and a uniform coverage of the sample surface by the layer. Fig. 6 shows the average weight of HP layers obtained by removing of these products by pickling, which enables the estimation of the layer thickness (Table 6). In this illustration, the area of the exposed sample is comprised. The changes of

average weight shown in Fig. 5 are affected by the continual dissolution of the zinc substrate, while Fig. 6 calculates the average weight of the HP layer based on the weight difference before (with already formed layer) and after pickling. The change in weight of the HP layer gradually increases up to 24 h of exposure at 25 and 37 °C in the bath type "1" (Fig. 6a). The highest changes in the weight were determined for the layer formed during the exposure at 37 °C while in the case of 25 °C, the increase was gentler. If we consider the size of the standard deviation in the case of weight change at 25 °C and after 24 h, then a slight decrease would also occur. A different trend was observed in the case of weight changes of the layer obtained at 50 °C when the weight of layer decreased after 24 h. In the bath type "2", the weight changes were more significant than in the bath type "1". Such increase in weight was observed for all phosphating conditions (Fig. 6b); although, the increase was slow during the exposure at 50 °C and weight was almost constant since 4 h of exposure. Rather slow increase in surface layer weight was observed during the 4 h of exposure at 25 °C followed by the sharp

Fig. 6. The average weight per unit area of the HP layer obtained at various times and temperatures in the bath a) type "1" and b) type "2" determined after pickling.

Table 6

The HP layer thickness obtained at various times and temperatures of exposures to the baths.

Time (h)	Layer thickness (pm)					
	Type "1"			Type "2"		
	25 °C	37 °C	50 °C	25 °C	37 °C	50 °C
1	41 ± 4	58 ± 5	145 ± 66	45 ± 4	53 ± 1	78 ± 12
2	46 ± 9	69 ± 9	231 ± 42	59 ± 22	68 ± 3	162 ± 83
4	66 ± 12	278 ± 23	306 ± 50	68 ± 3	204 ± 110	253 ± 11
6	86 ± 3	358 ± 1	339 ± 51	112 ± 35	271 ± 139	246 ± 47
24	217 ± 49	474 ± 49	192 ± 21	530 ± 214	591 ± 70	287 ± 14

increase in the average weight of the layer (Fig. 6b). The final weight change of the layer formed at 37 °C was the highest across all the conditions, if we take into account the average value (Fig. 6a, b). It is necessary to point out that in the case of results concerning the bath type "2", 25 °C, there is a large standard deviation, and with consideration of such a range, the situation would approach 37 °C condition. The calculated thickness listed in Table 6 was calculated according to Eq. (3). The high deviations of the values of layer thickness relates to the formation of a non-uniform HP layers shown in Figs. 1 and 3. To determine the thickness, the surface layers were dissolved in chromic acid (0.5 g·L⁻¹ CrO₃ according to ASTM E407 standard) at 75 ± 1 °C, followed by weighing to achieve constant weight. Although this method is generally reliable for thickness determination, in our case, under these conditions, an uneven layer was formed. Large portions of the layer, resembling lumps, were present only in a few places on the surface, necessitating their dissolution. We documented this with microscope images (Figs. 1, 3) to draw it. Consequently, there are high deviations in some measurements. This uneven layer formation distorts the thickness, and due to the substantial deviation, it is not feasible to consider the value by simply adding or subtracting the error for the overall thickness of the layer created on the surface. The thicker layers were measured after the exposure in the bath type "2" and the thickest one was determined to be 591 ± 70 pm at 37 °C for 24 h. On the contrary, the layers formed during the exposure at 50 °C exhibited the thickest layer from the beginning of exposure in comparison with both temperatures, but the final thickness was the thinnest. This result applies to both types of baths.

The surface was analyzed using a confocal microscope and the roughness of the obtained layers is represented as the arithmetical mean

height (S_a parameter, Fig. 7a, b). This parameter is used generally to evaluate surface roughness and expresses the mean difference in the height of each point compared to the arithmetical mean of the plane (surface). The results of roughness belonging to the layers obtained after the exposure in the bath type "1" clearly show that the temperature significantly affected the roughness of the surface. The lowest roughness was observed in the case of samples exposed to 25 °C for each time (Fig. 7a). A similar roughness was determined for the samples exposed to 37 °C for 1–6 h followed by a sharp increase after 24 h of the exposure. Although the formed layer at 50 °C seemed to be the smoothest after 24 h (Fig. 1), its roughness was the highest. Such high roughness was most likely caused by the presence of dimples as the zinc substrate was not covered by HP completely (Fig. 2). This will be discussed in more detail later. The resulted roughness was completely different when the samples were phosphated in the bath type "2". The values of the S_a parameter were generally higher than that of in the bath type "1" (Fig. 7b). The surfaces were the roughest after the exposure at 25 °C. A similar roughness was determined for the samples exposed within 2–6 h regardless of the conditions. In the case of the samples phosphated at 50 °C, the surfaces were the smoothest and even the lowest roughness among all exposed surfaces was observed after 1 and 24 h. Other surface roughness parameters and surface profiles are shown in the Supplementary data. The S_a parameter for the initial substrate was determined to be 0.09 ± 0.014 before the exposure.

3.3. Dissolution rate

Fig. 8a, b displays the dissolution rate of the layered substrate during

Fig. 7. The roughness of obtained layers after various phosphating conditions.

Fig. 8. Dissolution rate of layered substrate during various times and temperatures in the bath a) type "1" and b) type "2".

the exposure and corresponding evolution of pH. It can be seen that the dissolution rate increased with time in both types of baths. The highest dissolution rate in the case of in the bath type "1" was observed at 37 °C which corresponds with the amount of the released Zn²⁺ ions (see Supplementary data) and the increasing pH value. The dissolution rate determined for the reaction conditions: 25 and 50 °C, 24 h, were approximately similar. Such observation corresponds with Table 6 and the results of the AAS analysis. The amount of released Zn²⁺ ions for material with layer obtained at 50 °C for 24 h in bath type "1" increased, but the layer became thinner according to previous results. Such behavior could be associated with spalling of the layer during the process. The dissolution of the hopeite layer can be excluded because hopeite is insoluble under this condition. In the bath type "2" (Fig. 8b), the dissolution rate increased with temperature together with pH and the amount of Zn²⁺ ion (see Supplementary data).

The crystal morphology of HP coating is further affected by the Zn²⁺ concentration in the solution. The results of AAS, listed in Supplementary data, represents the increasing amount of Zn²⁺ in the bath with the prolongation of exposure when 5 samples were exposed to the same time and gradually, the samples were taken out one by one at time intervals

(see Experiment). The crystal morphology of HP coating gradually became regular with the morphology of cubic-block shape crystal during the exposure at 25 and 37 °C in both types of baths (Figs. 1 and 3). It seems that there is a limit in Zn²⁺ concentration suggesting the possible solution saturation. The concentration of Zn²⁺ ions always reached the value 2750 mg·L⁻¹ at 37 °C in the bath type "1" and at 25; 37; 50 °C in the bath type "2" after 24 h. The final concentration was independent of temperature. The moderate temperature of 25 °C allowed the formation of the thinnest and the lightest layer for the first 6 h of exposure. It is supposed that the growth kinetics is controlled effectively by the Zn²⁺ concentration in the solution. Based on these findings, the saturation time was determined by fitting polynomial curves (we consider the same running for all curves up to 6 h) to the dissolution rate data, as shown in Fig. 9. The corresponding values are listed in Table 7. It is evident from the results that the longest saturation time was observed at 37 °C which corresponds with thicker layer in comparison with 25 and 50 °C. At these temperatures, the saturation time was estimated to be approximately 10 h of exposure and therefore, the obtained layers were thinner.

Fig. 9. The dependence of dissolution rate on exposure time for determination of supersaturation time.

Table 7
Estimation of the saturation time.

Type of bath	Temperature (°C)	Time of saturation (h)
"1"	25 °C	10.9
	37 °C	12.6
	50 °C	10.7
"2"	25 °C	10.7
	37 °C	13.7
	50 °C	9.2

3.4. Test on extracts

The results indicating the potential toxicity of extracts towards L929 and hFOB 1.19 cell lines are presented in Fig. 10 and Tables S9 and 10 in Supplementary data. According to the recommendations for both cell

lines, the extracts for L929 and hFOB 1.19 were prepared in MEM and DMEM/Ham's F-12, respectively. This may cause different corrosion behavior leading to the various content of released Zn^{2+} ions. As a results and together with other factors (pH, other kinds of released ions, impurities), differences in observed cell viability can be observed. In our case, the concentration of released Zn^{2+} ions (determined using the ICP-MS method) was generally higher in DMEM/Ham's F-12 indicating slightly higher corrosion rate of the material in this medium.

In the undiluted extracts (100 %), the cell viability of both kind of cells was below 40 % except the material prepared in the bath of type "2" and exposure at 37 °C for 1 h. In this case, almost 100 % viability has been observed. When the extract concentration was diluted to 50 %, the cell viabilities of all samples were increased significantly for both cell lines. However, majority of extracts except samples prepared at 37 °C for 1 h in both types of baths remained still toxic for L929 with the cell

Fig. 10. Relative metabolic activity of L929 and hFOB 1.19 cells after 1 day of incubation with materials extracts. Metabolic activity is expressed as a percentage (negative control of sole medium - represents 100 %). Error bars indicate the sample standard deviation of six measurements. The concentration of Zn in $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ measured by ICP-MS is in Tables S9 and S10 (see Supplementary data).

viabilities close to the 70 %. The situation was even better for 50 % extracts and their effect on hFOB 1.19. In this case, extracts from the samples prepared at 37 °C for 1 and 6 h and 50 °C for 1 h in the bath type "2" were distinguished by cell viability over 80 % showing grade 1 cytotoxicity. Samples, prepared at 37 °C for 1 and 6 h and 50 °C for 1 h in the bath type "1", showed cell viability over 70 % for one sample from triplicate, other two samples were characterized by insufficient cytocompatibility, which in sum lead to the high values of standard deviations. It is worth to mention that similar behavior was observed for the non-treated samples of the zinc alloy indicating that the beneficial effect of the bath type "2" on cytocompatibility of hFOB 1.19 is rather controversial. On the contrary, the positive effect of surface treatment in the bath type "1" at specific conditions has clearly positive impact on material cytocompatibility towards hFOB 1.19.

The concentration of ions in extracts is one of the key points responsible for toxicity effect on cells. In this work, we have tracked the concentration of the Zn^{2+} , where we expected the dominant effect on cytotoxicity. However, there are also other ions in extracts like Mg^{2+} and Sr^{2+} . Their concentration is extremely low, and magnesium is also present in MEM and DMEM itself. The cytotoxicity of Mg^{2+} is low [50], especially compared to the Zn^{2+} ions. The concentration of Sr^{2+} ions was extremely low, maximum being $400 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ (see Tables S9 and S10 in Supplementary data). Verberckmoes et al. observed no toxic effect of Sr on osteoblasts up to $100 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ [51]. Overall, the influence of Mg^{2+} and Sr^{2+} on the cytotoxicity can be neglected [52–55]. Based on the obtained results, L929 cells were metabolically active in extracts with concentration of Zn below $50 \text{ }\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, while hFOB 1.19 cells were metabolically active in diluted extracts with concentration of Zn below $70 \text{ }\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$.

3.5. Cell adhesion

Although direct contact test is not a standardized method, it may bring further information about the possible cytotoxicity of the material, including not only the effect of released ions, but also chemical and physical variety of the surface and its roughness. The contact test was performed on the hFOB 1.19 cell line, where the colonization of the material and the morphology of the cells were evaluated using fluorescence microscopy. In the representing figures (Fig. 11), nuclei are

stained blue and F-actin is stained red. The number of nuclei has been determined using ImageJ software.

Although the cells on all Zn samples with surface layer and also on non-coated substrate were alive, they were distinguished by round shape, representing not healthy conditions of the cells. On the contrary, spread cells were observed on Ti control samples. The quantity of observed nuclei is listed in Fig. 11. It is evident that the number of nuclei was significantly decreased on all samples compared to titanium (ANOVA followed by Tukey test). No other statistical difference was found. Those results clearly correspond with the results of the tests on the extracts. Near the sample surface, the concentration of released ions would be at least the same as the concentration of ions in non-diluted extracts, i.e., higher than $70 \text{ }\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (for Zn^{2+}) which was estimated as the threshold cytotoxic concentration for the hFOB 1.19 cells.

3.6. Antibacterial activity

E. coli and *S. epidermidis* strains were used to test the antibacterial effect of the investigated materials. Fig. 12 illustrates the example results from the drip test (12 drops of bacterial suspension on each plate). Bacterial colonies in each drop were calculated and compared to negative (unaffected) control. Fig. 12a shows the bacterial counts of *E. coli* compared to the unaffected control. Cu used as a positive (antibacterial) control showed antibacterial effect after 4 h-incubation. But also, samples prepared in the bath type "1" at 50 °C for 1 and 24 h had strong antibacterial effect reducing the colony count after 4 h to 50 and 35 %, respectively. Furthermore, all materials with the surface layers prepared in the bath type "1" and "2" have reached better conditions compared to the non-coated substrate, where the bacterial counts of *E. coli* reached almost 120 % indicating even growth of bacterial colonies.

Fig. 13b shows the bacterial counts of *S. epidermidis* compared to the unaffected control. Cu used as a positive (antibacterial) control showed the strongest antibacterial effect after 4 h-incubation. In this case, surface treatment had effect on bacterial colonies reducing the colony counts for all samples compared to both untreated zinc alloy and Ti. The highest antibacterial effects have been observed again for the samples prepared in the bath type "1" at 50 °C for 1 and 24 h reaching the colony counts about 60 %.

Fig. 11. hFOB 1.19 cells on a) sample 37 °C, 1 h, bath type "1", b) sample 50 °C, 1 h, bath type "1", c) sample without the treatment, d) Ti control after one day incubation. Nuclei are stained blue, F-actin is stained red. Scale bar equals to 50 μm .

Fig. 12. Evaluation of the number of colonies by the drip test: a) negative control, b) positive control (Cu), c) sample 37 °C, 6 h, bath type "1", d) sample without treatment. The PCA dishes were divided into the 12 fields, 25 μ L of the suspension was pipetted into each of them, 4 technical replicates from each triplicate were made.

Fig. 13. Antibacterial activity expressed as CFU of a) *E. coli*, and b) *S. epidermidis* colony numbers (in %) compared to unaffected control after incubation with materials. Error bars represent the standard deviation of three tested samples. Differences ($p < 0.05$) among groups are indicated by letters (one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey test, see Tables S11 and S12 in Supplementary data).

4. Discussion

4.1. Introduction to issue

Zinc alloys generally belong in the group of so-called biodegradable or absorbable metals. The degradation rate of pure zinc was indicated as moderate, and specifically, the corrosion rate for Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloys tested in this work was determined to be around $0.36 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{a}^{-1}$ in the as-ECAPed state [38]. However, the gradual degradation of zinc alloy is associated with the release of zinc cations into the surroundings of tissue, which could cause the exceeding of critical concentration and a possible cytotoxic effect [56]. Such a problem could be effectively solved by the application of coatings on zinc alloys. This surface modification easily allows controlling the ion release from alloy during its degradation, especially in the initial stage after the implantation, when the injured tissue surrounding the implant is most sensitive. Moreover, HP, as one of the possible candidates for coating, is claimed to be promising one, providing excellent biocompatibility and chemical stability [3]. Our study focused on the coating of biodegradable Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy and demonstrated the effect of two types of bath and different

phosphating conditions on the formed layer, its characteristics, and subsequent cell response.

4.2. Phosphating process

First, the formed layer was studied from the phase composition aspect. Only the HP layer formed on the zinc alloy substrate under all exposure conditions (Table 5). The formation of HP is advantageous due to its stable chemical properties and good biocompatibility [3,35]. This is a typical phase arising on a substrate submerged in a phosphating bath containing phosphoric acid independently on the further composition of bath or exposure conditions [16]. Therefore, its formation was expected under selected conditions. The only requirement and prerequisite are the presence of Zn^{2+} ions in the solution for the formation and growth of the HP layer. Both were secured by the pH value of the phosphating bath and the individual components present in the bath. The initial pH value was measured to be 1.81 ± 0.03 for bath type "1" and 1.50 ± 0.05 for bath type "2", respectively after mixing. Acidic pH supported the dissolution of zinc alloy substrate through self-corrosion and the releasing and the presence of Zn^{2+} (aq) in the bath as can be assumed

from the Pourbaix diagram of zinc [57]. The substrate, especially zinc, was attacked immediately by the acid bath after immersion. As the self-corrosion of the zinc alloy substrate continued, more and more Zn^{2+}

from the substrate and PO_4^{3-} from the bath are present which resulted in a large amount of Zn^{2+} in the bath as was confirmed by AAS (see Supplementary data). The presence of zinc cations was sufficient for starting the gradual formation of insoluble HP crystals and promoted the whole process. As their concentration increased in the bath, the HP precipitation became easier and faster as was shown in the work of N.V. Phuong et.al [16] followed by a slowdown in layer growth over time. The whole process can be described according to the reactions as follows (Eqs. (4)–(8)):

The formation of HP thus consisted of three stages: i) dissociation of phosphoric acid (takes place in three steps), ii) the self-corrosion of the zinc alloy substrate and iii) crystallization and growth of HP crystals. Since phosphoric acid behaves as triprotic acid in solution meaning, three ionizable hydrogen atoms and hydrogen ions are lost sequentially. The reduction of phosphate is very slow reaction, but it could occur locally. The self-corrosion of zinc alloy substrate consumes hydrogen ions occurring in the bath [8,24] leading to the promotion of ionization of phosphate groups. The crystallization and growth of the HP layer were then allowed due to the diffusion of released Zn^{2+} [8], which could be seen from the dependence shown in Fig. 6. Its formation was accompanied by a slight increase in pH values (Fig. 5). The slight increase of pH value was expected according to the observation of H.S. Bender et.al [24] and could be associated with either the possible ongoing reaction, during which OH^- ions formed (Eq. (9)):

or the reduction of the hydrogen ions (Eq. (10)), which were reduced simultaneously at the micro cathode sites:

Neutralization according to the Eq. (11) must also occur in the bath.

The Eq. (9) occurs in an acidic environment due to the presence of an excess of acids (H^+), the pH value decreases, leading to a shift in the equilibrium of the reaction towards the production of more hydroxide ions (OH^-). However, the resulted pHs did not exceed the crucial value of 3 [7] and thus, HP formed as a stand-alone. As was shown in other studies [18,20,49] and in Fig. 5, the conversion ratio of coating caused the increase of pH in the bath as a result of ongoing reactions mentioned above. In the case of the coating obtained at 50 °C in the bath type "1", the decline of the average weight of the HP layer was observed which could relate to the dissolution of the coating. This one will be discussed later. During the coating process, bubbles in the bath were observed intensively suggesting that the reaction listed in Eq. (10) was in

progress. The bubbles of hydrogen also come from the formation of hopeite considering the following equation (Eq. (12)) [17,27,49]:

Besides the self-corrosion of zinc alloy, the hydrogen ions are also consumed by the reaction with NO_3^- ions [17], which are present in both types of baths (Eq. (13)):

The blends of nitrite and nitrate were claimed to be the best oxidizing agents for the improvements of the oxidation of hydrogen gas to water [24]. The formation of the HP layer was facilitated in the terms of thermodynamics, as well. The Gibbs free energy always moves to lower values to reach the stable state. The Zn^{2+} cations are coating-forming ions and were present freely in the bath due to the aforementioned self-corrosion of zinc alloy, which is an unstable state for them. Therefore, they started to react with anions produced by the dissociation of phosphoric acid leading to the formation of a layer. These ions thus moved in the direction of the layer formation, which was the stable condition for Zn^{2+} ions. The whole process is characterized as the competition between the self-corrosion of zinc alloy and the formation of the HP layer, especially in the case of shorter periods of exposure. On the contrary, the process was driven by the kinetics of HP layer formation in the case of prolonged times (24 h). This can be supported by the same concentration of released Zn^{2+} cations after 24 h at all temperatures (see Supplementary data).

4.3. Effect of the individual components of the baths, temperature, time, pH, and concentration of Zn^{2+}

The formation of HP, its shape, morphology, thickness, rate of nucleation, distribution, and weight changes were affected by the selected phosphating condition and the components in the bath. The components were added for the improvement of the speed of coating formation, crystallinity, and the size of the crystals in the coating.

4.3.1. Effect of the individual components of the baths and pH

Firstly, the effect of the individual components of the bath will be discussed. The bath type "1" contained NaF, *N*-Ethylethanamine, and 2,3-Dihydroxybutanenedioic acid in comparison with bath type "2". The roles of the individual components are described and labeled in the experimental part. Fluoride, nitrate compounds, and 2,3-Dihydroxybutanenedioic acid are used for improvements in the crystallinity of the HP coatings or in the sludge control. Both were reported as the most effective [24]. It is supposed that 2,3-Dihydroxybutanenedioic acid, preventing the formation of HPO_4^{2-} sludge and decreasing the pH of the bath according to work [17], changed mainly the pH which subsequently affected the obtained coating weight [25]. With the combination of zinc ions in the bath, the local increase in pH triggered the formation of thick and compact HP coatings. The initial value of pH after mixing of the bath was 1.81 ± 0.03 for bath type "1" and 1.50 ± 0.05 for bath type "2", respectively. The bath type "2" was more acidic although no 2,3-Dihydroxybutanenedioic acid was added. This could be explained by the addition of *N*-Ethylethanamine to the bath type "1", causing the increase in pH. The subsequent gradual increase of pH in both baths was associated with the formation of the coating layers. Nevertheless, the resulted pH did not exceed the range of 1.8–2.5 [17] in the bath type "2". Such value is critical for the formation of sludge [17], whose presence influenced the coating quality and lifetime of the phosphating bath [49]. On the contrary, the light transparent film covering the samples exposed

in the bath type "1" was observed visually and was removed by rinsing in ethanol. However, all the coated samples were rinsed to remove entrapped zinc phosphate solution in the coating and the recessed areas of the part after the phosphating process. This is also recommended because the pores or open areas are usually present in the phosphating coating and these parts have to be sealed [24] to prevent the subsequent affecting, e.g. cell testing. Although, the measured pH was higher in the bath type "1" than in the bath type "2", its value exceeded the value of 2.5. Thicker layer was then found after exposure in the bath type "2" (Fig. 6b). The self-corrosion of zinc alloy was less intense in the bath type "1" and sludge also formed and block the surface against the further formation of the HP layer. The increased pH also supports the formation rate of HP [49]. It is concluded that 2,3-Dihydroxybutanenedioic acid and *N*-Ethylethanamine affected the quality of the obtained HP layers. The layer of HP obtained after the exposure in the bath type "2" (Fig. 3) is more discontinuous in comparison with the layer obtained in the bath type "1" (Fig. 1). 2,3-Dihydroxybutanenedioic acid mainly ensured the coating process without the formation of a large portion of sludge with a negative effect on the HP layer. The SEM micrographs (Figs. 1 and 3) shown that the areas of Mg_2Zn_{11} phase were more etched in alloy exposed to the bath type "2" in comparison with the substrate in the bath type "1". Because the composition of the bath type "1" was inspired by a bath designed for magnesium alloy [17], NaF was added to the bath for zinc alloys coated in this work. It seems that NaF ensured the inhibition of the corrosion of the Mg_2Zn_{11} phase and restrain the formation of uneven coating. The tested zinc alloy contained a magnesium-based phase, specifically Mg_2Zn_{11} . Therefore, the mentioned phase can be protected using NaF enabling the formation of MgF_2 [28,58]. The presence of MgF_2 was confirmed by XRD analysis (Fig. 14, Table 8). Detail of XRD is listed in Supplementary data. Detailed analysis of MgF_2 presence is shown in Supplementary data. The AAS analysis (see Supplementary data) also showed an increasing concentration of Zn^{2+} in the baths suggesting the intensive dissolution of the zinc matrix rather than the Mg_2Zn_{11} phase. Furthermore, HP formed firstly at areas of Mg_2Zn_{11} phase, which suppress further etching (Figs. 1, 3). It is concluded that less etched areas of Mg_2Zn_{11} phase and higher dissolving of zinc matrix were closely related to the presence of MgF_2 acting as a protection layer. In the bath type "2", the areas of the Mg_2Zn_{11} phase were not protected by MgF_2 , and the Sr-rich phase was found together with HP on the surface of the substrate (Fig. 4). The presence of the $SrZn_{13}$ phase on the surface suggests the intensive dissolving of the zinc matrix and Mg_2Zn_{11} phase as well, although the $SrZn_{13}$ phase is the least noble [38]. The $SrZn_{13}$ phase occurred inside the regions of the Mg_2Zn_{11} phase [59]. Therefore, this phase was protected by MgF_2 formed on the Mg_2Zn_{11} phase in the case of the bath type "1". As was proven, the $SrZn_{13}$ phase is the least noble compared to the Zn and Mg_2Zn_{11} phases indicating

Table 8

Quantitative phase analysis of MgF_2 formed on Mg_2Zn_{11} phase exposed to the bath type "1" at 25 °C for 1 h determined from GID measurement with an incident angle of 0.5°.

Phase	Phase composition (wt%)
Mg_2Zn_{11}	50
Zn	29
HP	8
MgF_2	13

tendency to the precipitation of strontium compounds protecting the $SrZn_{13}$ phase. Suggested compounds that can be present in the solution are $Sr(OH)_2$ or $Sr(NO_3)_2$. However, these compounds dissolve in acidic environments. We analyzed the regions of Sr occurrence using various experimental techniques, but the results were ambiguous. Thus, we provide chemical composition determined using EDS analysis (wt%): Zn 72.3; Na 9.1; O 8.9, Sr 7.5, and P 2.2, and assume that the $SrZn_{13}$ phase is covered by thin layer of Sr-based compounds. Sodium nitrate and nitrite were effective in accelerating the speed of the reaction. Both consume hydrogen ions leading to the increasing of local pH at the substrate-bath interface [17,49]. Subsequently, HP may form more easily as the pH increases. Based on the SEM micrographs (Figs. 1 and 3), HP was present over the whole samples and the covering of the substrate differs in only the amount of formed HP. The addition of sodium nitrate and nitrite helped with the homogeneous precipitation of HP on more sites of substrate surface in agreement with other studies [17] and HP did not form only in the areas of the Mg_2Zn_{11} phase. It is claimed that the individual components of both baths affected mainly the distribution of HP over the substrate surface, its thickness and the pH of the baths.

4.3.2. Effect of the temperature and time

Another significant parameter influencing the coating process is the selected temperature. The effect of temperature consists in a crucial factor for crystal nucleation [11]. It has been observed that the increase in temperature led to an increase in the extent of metal dissolution and coating weight [20]. The increasing temperature accelerates the formation of HP nuclei as was shown in Table 5 and thus, higher temperature supported the quicker formation of the nucleus [11]. The HP's formation is thus controlled by the kinetic of the ongoing reactions. This phenomenon subsequently affected the occurrence of HP. SEM-EDS maps (Fig. 2) show that the zinc substrate was partially covered by HP after the exposure at 37 °C while only small isles of zinc remained uncovered after the exposure at 50 °C (Fig. 2). The coverage by HP is directly associated with the chemical composition of the bath. The HP nuclei were observed firstly on the Mg_2Zn_{11} phase as was mentioned

Fig. 14. GID data with single identified phases plotted underneath.

above and shown in Fig. 1. As was shown in work [19], the number of nuclei increases also with the presence of fluoride ions in the bath. Therefore, the rate of nucleation could be ascribed to the combination of using fluorides in the phosphating bath and higher temperature. On the other hand, the increasing temperature supported the formation of a continuous and much smoother layer with no large polyhedral crystals. The layers obtained in the bath type "1" at 25 °C for 24 h were composed of smaller crystals of HP than the substrate exposed in the bath type "2". The reduction in the size of the crystals was caused by the fluoride ions under this temperature [19]. With higher applied temperatures, this difference disappeared, and larger HP crystals formed rather during exposure in the bath type "1". The highest temperature of 50 °C led to the formation of a continuous layer with no larger crystals. The smoother and more compact layer was then obtained after the exposure in the bath type "1" at 50 °C for 24 h. The formation of the compact layer was affected in this case by the presence of fluoride ions as was described in literature [19]. In both bath types, the use of high temperature for the phosphating process exhibited a beneficial impact on the continuity, compactness, and smoothness of the layer. The same goes for the time of the exposure because the prolonged time allowed for a longer time for the dissolution of substrate and growth of HP. The positive effect of increasing temperature on the compactness of the coating which was denser is in good agreement with another work [11]. The changes in the average weight of the HP layer gradually decreased in both baths at 50 °C (Fig. 6a, b) during exposure suggesting the probable dissolving of HP under these conditions. Although the solubility of HP decreased in the solution of the phosphoric acid with increasing temperature [60], at the temperatures of 50 °C, the situation is changed and the weight of the

HP layer decreased in this work. However, it was not detrimental to the compactness or smoothness of the layer because no significant or new voids, cracks, or any other damage were observed (Figs. 1, 3). The present voids were rather associated with the incomplete coverage by the HP, not with the dissolving of HP. This was visible from the edges of voids which were not fully closed, and prolongation of time was expected to close them. The decreasing layer weight could be associated with the spalling of the coating as was observed in earlier [20]. Each bath was filtered after the exposure and no particles were found. However, the presence of nanoparticles is not excluded. It seems that the increase in coating weight led to the increase of pH in the bath and it went for both types of baths. The conversion into the coating increased with an elevated temperature and time, and the pH value increased as a result of the depolarization reaction, in which H^+ ions are reduced, and due to the gradual depletion of hydrogen phosphate ions from the bath.

As was described above, the smoothest layer was obtained after the exposure in the bath type "1" at 50 °C for 24 h (Fig. 1). However, obtained roughness indicated the opposite result (Fig. 7). The measured S_a parameter was one of the highest. Such high roughness of the smooth layer could be attributed to the presence of voids/uncovered substrate shown in Figs. 1, 2b. The difference between the layer and zinc alloy substrate affected the S_a parameter significantly. This difference increased as the layer was thicker. The obtained layers were thicker after the exposure at 50 °C in the bath type "1" (Table 6). The measurement of the S_a parameter expresses an absolute value of the difference in the height of each point compared to the arithmetical mean of the surface. Therefore, the S_a parameter was influenced by the presence of small deeper uncovered areas while the almost whole surface was covered.

Fig. 15. 3D profiles of the samples exposed to 50 °C for 24 h in a) bath type "1" and b) bath type "2".

Roughness was thus misrepresented in this case. This is illustrated in Fig. 15a, where the hollows are obvious in the same regions. The roughness of layers was generally increased after exposure in the bath type "2" (Fig. 7b). However, the S_a parameter was not affected by the difference in the highest and lowest measured regions. These regions arose in the large number and the surface was more wrinkled (Figs. 3, 14b). The rest of surface roughness parameters are listed in Supplementary data.

4.3.3. Effect of the concentration of Zn^{2+}

Less concentration of Zn^{2+} ions after the exposure in the bath type "1" was caused by the slower dissolving of Mg_2Zn_{11} phase and zinc substrate and kinetic of HP formation in the case of 25 °C and more extensive covering by HP coating in the case of 50 °C (Fig. 1). This means that the increase of the Zn^{2+} concentration in the solution no longer affected the crystal morphology, which was also suggested in another work [61], if we prolonged the time of exposure. Therefore, the dissolution rate of the alloy and subsequent Zn^{2+} concentration in the solution mainly affect the crystal structure morphology. Limitations in the changes of morphology and crystallization conditions depend on the degree of saturation of the phosphating solution. On the other hand, the fast saturation degree reduces the energy barrier necessary for overcoming crystal nucleation, thereby nucleation rate resulting in the evolution of the layer growth is accelerated [61]. The moderate temperature of 25 °C allowed the formation of the thinnest and the lightest layer for the first 6 h of exposure, which is related to the low saturation degree and thus relatively high nucleation barrier.

Due to the changes in coating weight, the kinetics of coating formation could not be provided. Such results give only information about the amount of the coating formed on the substrate and no information regarding the kinetics. For the description of the kinetics and mechanism of the phosphating process, the potential-time measurements are necessary for their proper determination [20]. Nevertheless, the above-described results and the outline shown in the work [24] provide the obvious kinetic variables of the process consisting of three competitive reactions simultaneously occurring: formation of nuclei, homogeneous or heterogeneous pickling of metal surface, and heterogeneous growth of HP. Each step is influenced by the applied phosphating conditions and the presence of compounds in the phosphating bath.

4.4. Cytotoxicity

The cytotoxicity of the studied materials estimated by *in vitro* test has been performed using standard extract test and contact test. For cytotoxicity testing, two types of cells were used. Murine fibroblast cell line L929 were chosen as first, because the ISO 10993-5 standard [42] mentions it as a possible cell model to be used for *in-vitro* biomaterial testing. Further, human fetal osteoblast cell line hFOB 1.19 were used, because it is not cancerous, is conditionally immortalized and has the characteristics of osteoblasts [62] and, therefore, represents a close model to *in vivo* conditions. For the further cytotoxicity tests with hFOB 1.19, we omitted samples exposed to these conditions: 25 °C, 1 h for both types of baths, because the properties of the layers were the least suitable (uneven distributed crystals of hopeite over the surface).

During the tests on extracts, the tested materials were incubated in cultivation medium and then extracts were added to the cells. The extracts for L929 and hFOB 1.19 were prepared in different media (in MEM and in DMEM/Ham's F-12, respectively) according to the recommendations for the specific cell lines. However, such change may bring differences in obtained cytotoxicity results. The cytotoxicity of the materials evaluated based on the extract tests is related directly to the concentration of ions in the solution. Zn ions promote cell growth at low concentrations and inhibit cell growth at high concentrations [63]. Their concentration is affected by the corrosion process of materials with higher corrosion rates and therefore increased release of Zn^{2+} observed in DMEM/Ham's F-12 solution. The reason for such behavior

has been already observed in literature. DMEM/Ham's F-12 solution contains HEPES, which was previously shown to accelerate degradation of Mg-based [64] and Zn-based alloys [65]. Although the hFOB 1.19 are less sensitive to Zn ions than L929 [66], the higher concentration of Zn^{2+} ions in undiluted DMEM/Ham's F-12 extracts caused the toxicity to hFOB 1.19. We suppose that there was no negative influence of released Sr, because in other studies, the Sr concentration up to 6 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ had even beneficial effect on osteoblasts [67–69].

The concentration of released Zn^{2+} ions in extracts performed in MEM was approximately on the half and lower numbers compared to the concentrations in DMEM/Ham's F-12 solution. This resulted in higher viability of L929, although they are more sensitive to Zn^{2+} ions concentration [66]. Indeed, in one case (sample exposed to 37 °C, for 1 h in the bath type "2") the cell viability reached almost 100 % indicating no cytotoxicity of 100 % extract. Further dilution of extracts led to the improvement of cell viabilities for both cell lines which was related to the decrease of the Zn^{2+} ions in the solution. In sum, the non-toxic concentration of released Zn^{2+} (L929 cells were metabolically active in extracts with concentration of Zn below 50 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, hFOB 1.19 cells were metabolically active in diluted extracts with concentration of Zn below 70 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) are in good agreement with our previous findings [66]. Furthermore, Wang et al. [70] recommended 6–10-fold diluted extracts as the standard for evaluating the cell viability of degradable Mg-based biomaterials to bring adequate assessment compared to the *in-vivo* tests. Based on the obtained Zn^{2+} concentration in 100 % extracts and the results after 2-fold dilution, all studied materials would be distinguished by excellent cytocompatibility if 6-fold dilution would be applied.

4.5. Cell adhesion and bioimage evaluation

Cell adhesion and bioimage evaluation (Fig. 11) were performed on selected samples, exposed to 37 and 50 °C for 1 h in the bath type "1", as representatives of layers with lower roughness and of average results from previous tests. Cells on the surface of the tested materials were round in shape, which indicates non-healthy state. This impaired cell morphology was most probably caused by high local concentration of released Zn. During the contact test, the cells are in a small volume of media on sample surface. Therefore, released Zn^{2+} ions are concentrated close to the material surface affecting the cells viability. Similar results were observed in the case of zinc alloys [71]. Considering the rate of material dissolution during 24 h from extraction tests for samples exposed to 37 and 50 °C for 1 h in the bath type "1" (3.63 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, the average ion concentration in MEM solution equal to 69.85 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ is taken for calculation), the obtained value of zinc release is rather low. Still the Zn^{2+} ions are known to affect negatively cells in several ways causing death. 1. Excessive levels of zinc ions can lead to the production of reactive oxygen species within the cell. These are highly reactive molecules that can damage cellular components, including lipids, proteins, and DNA. This oxidative stress can disrupt cellular function and ultimately lead to a cell death. 2. Zinc ions can interfere with the activity of specific enzymes within the cell. Many enzymes require a precise balance of metal ions, including zinc, to function properly. If zinc ions are present in excess, they can disrupt the normal activity of these enzymes, leading to cellular dysfunction and death. 3. Zinc ions can interfere with the balance of other essential ions within the cell, such as calcium (Ca^{2+}). Cellular processes rely on a delicate balance of ions, and disturbances in this balance can have detrimental effects. Excessive zinc ions can disrupt calcium signaling, which is crucial for various cellular functions, including cell survival and death. It is known that direct cell cultivation on zinc materials reveals negligible cell survival despite good performance of Zn during *in vivo* tests. For example, Zn-Mg-Fe alloy was implanted for 24 weeks to treat mandibular fractures in canines and no significant increase in zinc concentration in blood was observed. New bone formation in the vicinity of zinc implant was comparable to the control group (titanium) [72]. This indicates the need to design a more

representative *in vitro* experiment for cytotoxicity investigation of Zn-based alloys and other biodegradable metals [73]. In our case, the observed *in vitro* corrosion rates (calculated from extract in medium) were much lower than recommended daily intake of Zn ($15 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$) [74].

4.6. Antibacterial properties

Antibacterial properties were tested using representatives of gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria; *i.e.* *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, respectively. *S. epidermidis* was found to be slightly more sensitive which is in agreement with the results of other authors [71]. Zn ions possess, in this case, antibacterial activity [75]. The thicker peptidoglycan layer in the cell wall of gram-positive bacteria causes higher resistance against penetration of ions into the cytoplasm. Sample, prepared at 50°C for 24 h in the bath type "1", had the most prominent antibacterial effect towards *E. coli*. This sample was distinguished by the lowest surface roughness. In general, increased surface roughness provides more opportunities for bacterial attachment, as the irregularities offer crevices and niches for bacteria to anchor themselves. Rough surfaces can facilitate the initial attachment of bacteria and enhance biofilm formation, which can lead to the persistent colonization and increased resistance to antimicrobial agents. Therefore, decreased surface roughness is suggested to have opposite effect. Such conclusion is supported by the observation of colony counts for *E. coli* in contact with the samples processed in the bath type "1" and "2" at 50°C . The surface of samples processed in the bath type "1" is characterized by lower roughness compared to the surface originated from the bath type "2" which well documents the reduced colony counts observed for the bath type "1". It is worth to mention that the reduction of colony counts for the bath type "1" are observed also for *S. epidermidis*, indicating the positive effect of decreased surface roughness on antibacterial properties.

4.7. Summary

The presented results offer suitable conditions for the coating of a biodegradable Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy. The positive influence of temperature, time, and additive compounds in the bath on the formation, composition, distribution, uniformity, and layer continuity has been demonstrated. Due to the acidic environment, the alloy underwent spontaneous dissolution, eliminating the need to add zinc compounds to the bath. Only a layer of hopeite was formed on the alloy. The addition of NaF resulted in the formation of MgF_2 on $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$, thereby protecting this phase along with the SrZn_{13} phase from etching and dissolution. Without the addition of NaF, the etching of $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$ occurred, and besides hopeite, a compound rich in Sr was present on the substrate's surface. At 50°C , there was more intensive dissolution of the matrix, leading to an increased layer weight. The nuclei of hopeite formed most rapidly at 50°C , and the resulting layers were the smoothest, most uniform, and compact after exposure at this temperature. Prolonging the phosphating time to 24 h also had a positive effect on the quality of the resulting layer. The bath type "2" could be better in terms of a lower number of compounds in the bath (phosphoric acid, sodium nitrate, and sodium nitrite) necessary for the formation of the desired layer. Distinctive condition of material surface had direct impact on *in vitro* biological behavior of studied materials indicating improved cytotoxicity and antibacterial effect for specific states. The tested samples exhibited cytotoxicity towards L929 cells and hFOB 1.19 cells in the test on extracts. The toxicity of the extracts was caused by the released Zn ions. The released amount of Zn was dependent on the medium type used. However, after two-fold dilution, the majority of the extracts was not toxic towards hFOB 1.19 cell line. None of the samples supported the growth of the cells on the surface. Samples with layers had generally better antibacterial properties, especially against *S. epidermidis*, compared to the samples without any treatment.

5. Conclusion

This study provided a characterization of the formation mechanism of hopeite on the promising biodegradable Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy via its self-corrosion process. The discovered findings from this publication can be summarized into the following points:

- 1) The self-corrosion of biodegradable Zn-0.8Mg-0.2Sr alloy in an acidic environment provides Zn^{2+} ion for the formation of the hopeite layer and the increased temperature (50°C) supports the faster formation of hopeite nuclei on material surface and improves the quality of layers.
- 2) The hopeite layer is accompanied by the compounds rich in Sr in the bath type "2" containing H_3PO_4 , NaNO_3 , NaNO_2 .
- 3) The addition of NaF to the bath type "1" causes the formation of MgF_2 on the $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_{11}$ phase, thereby protecting this phase from dissolution and preserving it in precipitated compounds.
- 4) The formation of surface layers improves the viability of cells in extracts from the tested materials indicating improved cytotoxicity.
- 5) The cytotoxicity of the undiluted extracts towards fibroblasts and osteoblasts was caused by the released Zn ions. Nevertheless, the released amount of Zn was lower than the recommended daily intake of Zn.
- 6) Samples with layers had generally better antibacterial properties, especially against *S. epidermidis*, compared to the samples without any treatment.
- 7) Smoother surface layers cause the suppression of bacterial viability indicating their potential as antibacterial protection on Zn-based alloys.

Funding

The authors would like to thank the Czech Science Foundation (project no. 23-05592S) for the financial support of this research. This publication was supported by the project "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Andrea Školáková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jan Pinc:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Eva Jablonská:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Tereza Školáková:** Investigation, Data curation. **Petr Vertát:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Barbora Janebová:** Investigation. **Anna Kutová:** Investigation. **Jaroslav Čapek:** Resources, Funding acquisition. **Klára Hosová:** Investigation. **Dalibor Vojtěch:** Resources, Funding acquisition. **Jiří Kubásek:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

The used data are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10795004>.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10795004>.

org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2024.130986.

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